

Observations on the ground running spider *Hirriusa arenacea* (Lawrence, 1927) from South Africa (Araneae: Philodromidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Peter Webb²‡

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda, dippenaaransie@gmail.com (South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) project manager) ²SANSA team member (deceased)

ABSTRACT: *Hirriusa arenacea* is a Southern African spider described by Lawrence (1927) as *Hirrius arenaceus* from Namibia. They are small ground-running spiders frequently encountered in sandy areas on the soil surface. Information on their general morphology, behaviour, and distribution in South Africa, as well as photographs of live specimens, is provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation biography, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The family Philodromidae, also known as running crab spiders, comprises a world fauna of 529 species in 29 genera, but the family's systematics is far from complete (World Spider Catalog, 2024). Several philodromid genera are monotypic, represented by only a few specimens.

Philodromidae remains one of the numerous taxa of the Afrotropical Region that have yet to be subjected to revisionary work. Six genera represented by 34 species are presently known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022, 2023), with only *Tibellus* Simon, 1875 that have been revised (Van den Berg, & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994). Members of the genus *Hirriusa* were frequently sampled during SANSA surveys (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Simon (1895) described the genus *Hirrius*, but the name was preoccupied, and a replacement name was provided by Strand (1932).

Some *Hirriusa* specimens sampled during the surveys were identified as *Hirriusa arenacea* (Lawrence, 1927). As little is still known about them, more information is here provided on their general morphology, behaviour, and distribution. Colour variations are discussed based on photographs of live specimens.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled ($n=92$) collected during SANSA surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. SANSA made requests for photographs of spiders for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), and several photographs of the species were received from the public.

TAXONOMY

Hirriusa arenacea (Lawrence, 1927)

Hirrius arenaceus Lawrence, 1927: 38 (mf); Lessert, 1933: 125 (f).
Hirriusa arenacea Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 9–10;
Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023: 174.

Diagnostic characteristics: (Figs 1 & 2). Size: TL females 7–8 mm, male 6–7mm. **Female:** cryptic; carapace brown, with broad paler median band; bordered by two broad darker bands from posterior eyes to posterior edge; margin with narrow pale margin broadening towards poster edge; whitish transverse band separating the anterior and posterior rows of eyes (Fig. 3); clypeus with a roughly triangular whitish marking (Fig. 7); row of strong setae on edge (Fig. 5). Carapace slightly flattened, as wide as long; sub-oval in outline; thoracic region evenly rounded, sloping gently posteriorly; fovea not very distinct. Eyes: 8 in 2 rows (4:4) (Figs 3, 7); both rows recurved; anterior row more so; median ocular quadrangle longer than wide, narrower anteriorly (Figs 5, 7); anterior eyes larger than posterior eyes (Fig. 3).

Figures 1–3. *Hirriusa arenacea* from Aardvark Nature Reserve. 1. Female, dorsal view. 2. Male, dorsal view. 3. Female lateral view. Photos: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–8. *Hirriusa arenacea*. 4. Female from Aardvark Nature Reserve, body dorsal view. 5. Male from Aardvark Nature Reserve, body dorsal view. 6. Male body dorsal view in alcohol. 7. Eye pattern, anterior view. 8. Integument. Photos: 4,5,7. Peter Webb. 6. ASD. 8. Rudy Jocqué.

Sternum and coxae yellow. Abdomen oval; covered with squamous setae plumose at their bases (Fig. 7); sometimes smaller patches of strong white-tipped setae present in patches of brown or yellowish setae (Fig. 4). According to Lawrence (1927) this species shows a fair amount of variation, some specimens being more darker coloured than others and in some the abdomens are almost without markings. There is also variation in the shape of the epigyne as seen in Figs 9–12. Legs slender, arranged sideways, similar in length variegated; with dense setae. **Male:** (Figs 2, 5, 6) resemble the female in shape and colour but with slightly smaller bodies and with the legs longer and slender (Figs 16–17). The male palp (Figs 13–15).

LIFESTYLE

They are small ground-running spiders frequently encountered in sandy areas on the soil surface and, owing to their cryptic colouration, they are well camouflaged and not easily seen. Their movements are erratic but swift and their claw tufts and scopulae enabling speedy movement. Their laterigrade legs and flat bodies also allow them to hide in crevices. The egg-sacs are covered with sand and deposited under stones or debris on the ground.

Hirriusa arenacea are known from the more arid regions in South Africa, Botswana and Namibia. They were frequently collected from pitfall traps in Desert, Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Nama-Karoo, Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes.

Hirriusa arenacea readily feed on the termites in the laboratory and may be an important predator of them. In the Northern Cape they were also sampled from pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013; Haddad *et al.*, 2004).

Several of the SANSA surveys where the species was recorded was undertaken in areas with a high termite activity: Dendron in the Limpopo Province (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978); Benfontein Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2023) and Tierberg Long Term Ecological Research site (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

Figures 9–15. *Hirriusa arenacea*. 9–10. Line drawings of epigyne showing the variation. 11–12. Epigyne. 13–15. Male palp. Photos: 9,10, After Lawrence (1927). 15. After Lessert (1933). 13. ASD. 14. Rudy Jocqué.

Figures 16–17. Male from Aardvark Nature Reserve. Photos: Peter Webb

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 17): **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Cradock (-32.10, 25.37); Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (-33.76, 24.81). **Free State:** Luckhoff, Farm Bankfontein-Nama Karoo veld (-30.063, 24.897); Golden Gate Highlands National Park (-28.31, 28.37); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Qwa Qwa Nature Reserve, Spelonken (-28.28, 28.38); Allemanskraal Dam (-28.17, 27.10); Pinekloof (-29.14, 27.24); Groenhoek (Berghut) (-30.16, 27.13). **Limpopo:** Ndengeza (-23.316, 30.411); Vyeboom (-23.1439, 30.3797); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Limpopo Valley, farm Stoke (-22.476, 29.870); Dendron, Farm Amsterdam (-23.367, 29.317). **Northern Cape:** Riemvasmaak (-28.53, 20.29); 4 km W of Hopetown (-29.62, 24.06); Klein Pakkuil farm (-28.48, 23.72); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Prieska, Green Valley Nuts Estate (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Strydenburg, between Britstown and Hopetown (-29.95, 23.68); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Benfontein, Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Oryx Game Farm, Kuruman (-28.419, 22.175); Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42). **North West:** Stella 30.5 km N (-26.29, 24.78); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West from following farms: Farm 151b (-32.32, 22.44); Farm Alexanderskraal (-32.58, 22.71); Farm Bokvlei (-32.43, 22.35); Farm De Pannen (-32.61, 23.10); Farm Eerste Water (-32.61, 23.10); Farm Groot Kraanvogelfontein (-32.92, 22.64); Farm Juriesfontein (-32.53, 23.43); Farm Kantkraal (-33.28, 23.22); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088); Tierberg (-33.216, 22.033).

Figure 17. Distribution of *Hirriusa arenacea*.
Credit: S. Foord.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

The species has a wide distribution and has been recorded from six provinces. It has been collected from several protected areas such as Aardvark Nature Reserve (Figs 4 & 5, 16 & 17); Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020); Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Benfontein Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2023); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023); Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2023); Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018). No conservation actions are recommended.

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